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TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrofood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agro-food trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrofood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations

1. Background

1.1 TCforBE aims and objectives.

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrofood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has becoming increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agro-food trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrofood systems**. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrofood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrofood systems.

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrofood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity and equity.

- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agro-food system stakeholders.

1.2 TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders.

To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low and middle income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics
Cameroon	Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerging cocoa agrofood systems export timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP) trade, mining • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • Sustainability landscape initiatives (SLI) e.g. Dja Green cocoa landscape • Large areas of rapidly degrading high-biodiversity forests, increasing agriculture
Colombia	Eastern Plains Llanos Orientales Magdalena River Cauca River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, and reforestation programs. • Megadiverse landscapes • 20% in conservation and 30% in communal lands but facing violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence. • Appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders
Kenya	Mau forest – Masai - Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wetlands - expanding rice production and fish farming, and grasslands with grazing systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP-horticulture systems • Medium levels of telecoupling • Large areas of high biodiversity forest ecosystems & extensive agriculture • Regenerative change & SLIs: MaMaSe program
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grasslands (grazing systems) and tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • SLIs: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration

2. Introduction

This document explores Transdisciplinarity, Co-Production, Participatory Action Research and Multi-Stakeholder Social Learning approaches, to inform the TCforBE project design, especially in Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya as part of WPs 2, 4 and 5. The approaches are inter-related and it is ongoing work in the project to clarify and decide how to apply such an approach. This guidance suggests nested learning cycles as a way of engaging with stakeholders in learning for transformative change. We need to reconcile this approach with the resources and skills within the consortium.

3. Practical Steps

3.1 TCforBE social learning processes

SL is part of the overall TC4Be project approach and central to WP 2, 4 and 5. The Integrated Plan for WP 4 and 5 includes an outline of the social learning process. This is summarized below.

Please spend time to acquaint yourself both with the basic process, the background academic justification and project commitments to EU.

Consistent methodology: Note that we should follow a consistent methodology for learning cycles by learning alliances. There is ample scope for flexibility as the process goes along but the process needs to be clearly structured to act as a compass for people who are exploring things in new ways (especially researchers!)

Reduced ambition – 1 Landscape per country: we recommend a focus on 1 landscape per country for learning processes and allocation of funding to complete the learning cycle *properly*. Resources are being transferred to country level from WU and UoG to make this process easier and fund learning activities.

Sequence: On reflection, and to build consistency, it is important to all start at landscape scale – plan these asap, and only later engage national stakeholders (apart from interviews done to gather policy data, inform about the project or as part of Q method for example which could start sooner). This avoids using up our precious resources in bringing stakeholders together in ways which are not consistent across the project and do not class as social learning cycles focused on transformative change. Engagement of national stakeholders should be postponed until we have built team capacity on learning processes focused upon transformative change and budgets amended accordingly. The findings from the landscape scale can then be taken up at national scale (Year 2), and then we go down again to landscape scale (year 3). Also we await some TC for BE researcher outputs e.g. EU transitions impact mapping in Amazon and Congo biomes.

Facilitation skills in our producer countries landscapes in Kenya, Colombia, and Cameroon are needed for structured learning processes involving multiple stakeholders, including capacity to challenge orthodoxies and create safe spaces for marginal voices. Please reflect in your project team on who has these skills or is willing to develop them.

Language –social learning is implemented through **cycles** (i.e. structured processes of co-design/ co-framing, co-learning and action, co-reflection (and evaluation)). The cohort that participates we can call a learning alliance. The process is a commitment to continued learning and action. It won't be possible to engage ALL stakeholders – more we are focused on building energy and commitment from a relatively small group but that covers diverse values (to be found in competing narratives for future sustainability).

Table 1: Proposed TCforBE Social Learning Process (which runs alongside the researcher-driven activities in this project and underpins them)

What	Who	When 2023/2024	Notes
Year 1			
Preparatory work to co-design social learning cycle methodology involving learning alliances at different scales	All; VN leads overall design as has project-wide SL role; Project Manager decides on design, budget etc. JQ supports as landscape co-lead. To be applied across all 3 countries (maybe EU)	Now until...	
Compare narratives to policies	WP 4		
Landscape Scale			
Preparatory work (initial mapping and exploratory discussions at local level)		Now	
Rural imaginaries co-design and implementation	VN co-design Implementation – country teams, with support from VN	Jan - April	
Selecting learning cycle participants (drawing on rural imaginaries) to reflect diverse values		April-May	
Initial Transformation workshop to kick off learning cycle. <i>In the workshop:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore pasts/future visions and how transformations might occur. • learning priorities relating to deep leverage points. • Plan joint learning activities (e.g. experiments, evidence reviews, field visits, festivals, joint studies) • Include workplan. Likely to split into sub-groups for learning activities. • Identify what participants aim to contribute to in terms of outcomes 	VN to co-design workshop with inputs from all – focus on TC in agrifood systems/landscapes. Teams to provide facilitation of the learning process	June - Dec	NB to manage expectations, but requires <u>budget allocations</u> to be made, as well as mobilizing the ongoing resources of participants. Online sharing can be facilitated, the process can draw upon related TC for BE research activities, but also research by others and IPLC knowledges.
Learning activities (in person, online etc)	Facilitated, tracked and documented by country teams, with back up from VI, VN, JH, XR etc.		
Reflection meetings and workshop	Co-design a workshop to reflect on TC futures, scenarios, pathways and LP learning insights (in person and online) and support actions.		

What	Who	When 2023/2024	Notes
Year 1			
Normally you repeat the above – rather than expecting participants to have got a long way in one cycle, i.e it is cumulative.			
Year 2 National scale learning process			
<p>Q method – key steps for discussion, but to identify the competing narratives currently in play in each country</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree on research questions (food, land, rural, economy transformations) • Develop a concourse (social media scraping/analysis; policy documents/websites etc) • Create a set of statements, • Conduct interviews to rank the statements with a group of stakeholders. • Conduct factor analysis • Interpret 	XR and VN to generate draft proposal methodology for comment	To confirm – post landscape scale	
Select learning process participants from those different narratives (to be pluralistic BUT with particular effort to give voice to narratives that challenge orthodoxies)			
Bring stakeholders together for initial TRANSFORMATION WORKSHOP using a method (methodology to be designed and shared in advance e.g. seeds of change methodology)	As above – similar methodology for workshop design. TC - just WHAT it would look like in future, but HOW to get there (Leverage Points). Identify learning themes (could be on LPs or contested narratives) to explore as mini-groups in the cohort of learners – each group will explore then bring back to the entire cohort of the learning alliance to share and reflect.		TC for BE research findings and from other research projects can be shared as and when available if we create learning alliances.
Conduct learning activities (and document/evaluate)	<p>Participants do joint learning activities (e.g. field visits, arts, experiments and pilots. They are in the lead, facilitated by us.</p> <p>Anticipated outcomes: Shared learning and capacity of stakeholders on TC strengthened and enhanced mobilization to act. Analysis of findings and insights (report/briefing/video)</p>		We explain to participants and stakeholders at the start that our funding is limited – but leave some budget to support facilitation, venues etc.

What	Who	When 2023/2024	Notes
Year 1			
			<p>but with clear expectations management – In some cases other organisations bring their on-going work so it is not always about new funding but providing them with a focal point and way of upscaling knowledge etc. Our research activities will also feed in.</p>
Reflection			
Repeat learning cycles (ongoing personal and face to face dialogues and deliberations) if energy and resources			

Fig.1. TC4BE transdisciplinary research process (WP4)

Learning cycle(s) & research activities at national scale

Figure 1: Learning cycle processes at national scale and linkages to research activities

Figure 2: A linear representation of the social learning process and the researcher-driven activities that will feed into this.

Researcher driven activities (shown in orange) feed into the learning processes which are more learner-driven involving a broad topic (transformative change, under which participants might select learning themes of interest to them).

Researcher driven activities at landscape scale include rural imaginaries, landscape scale Bayesian modelling, enterprise studies at landscape scale as well as other tasks such as in WP 1 and 2 which could provide useful information for sharing such as on the rights of nature or trade deals. This is combined with a social learning process.

At national scale – analyses of policies, trends and commodity / land use impacts, etc are researcher driven, alongside other inputs from WP 1 and 2.

A social learning process will bring national stakeholders together to learn about themes (under the broad TC banner) of interest to them.

4. Background, justification and explanation

4.1 What are transdisciplinarity, participatory action research, co-production and social learning approaches?

Transdisciplinary research (or TDR) is often confused with *multidisciplinary research* and *interdisciplinary research* (Lawrence et al., 2022). *Multidisciplinary research* cooperation of researchers from different disciplines seeking to address the same problem using their disciplinary concepts, methods, and knowledge (Thomas, et al., 2018). “draws on knowledge from different disciplines but stays within their boundaries” (Choi & Pak, 2006, p. 351). *Interdisciplinary research* harmonizes links between disciplines into a coordinated coherent whole (Choi & Pak, 2006), disciplinary knowledges (concepts, methods, and results) from different disciplines are integrated and one conceptual framework, methods, and results are developed (one common language) (Thomas, et al., 2018). It results in its own interdisciplinary concepts and methods and involves much closer interaction than multidisciplinary research (Thomas, et al., 2018). Multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary research are often *explicitly or implicitly* mentioned in definitions of TDR (Lawrence et al., 2022). TDR is not a replacement for multidisciplinary or interdisciplinary research, but it can complement it.

Trans- means **beyond, over or across**. TDR *transcends* disciplinary boundaries and uses knowledges and methods from various disciplines, similar to interdisciplinary research, but seeking to go beyond this. While there is growing demand and efforts to work in TDR ways, it is challenging, and approaches are not settled. TDR is a **process** in which disciplines are assembled and information is recombined according to Choi and Pak (2006, p. 357). In this process, academics (and others) puzzle about new potential connections that can result in the emergence of new ideas, concepts, methods, and empirical knowledge (Choi & Pak, 2006). However, TDR can go further and involve more direct and explicit exploration by research teams of the ethical and political tensions involved in their different methods (West et al, ref).

Different intensities identified of transdisciplinarity (Huutoniemi et al., 2010). For some authors, TDR is about ‘integration’, i.e. different degrees of knowledge integration may be involved (in problem definition, conceptualization, methods, and results) (Huutoniemi et al 2010). However, TRD also refers to a crossing of boundaries between science (and scientists) and society. In TDR the emergence of new ideas, methods and knowledge is rigorous from an academic perspective and is relevant to societal problems. This is because TDR involves academic and non-academic actors through a knowledge co-production process (Thomas et al., 2018). TDR to study governance of sustainability challenges implies integration of different academic disciplines and the participation of both scientific and non-scientific actors (Grange, 2017; Lang, et al., 2012).

The co-produced knowledge is rigorous from an academic perspective and relevant to complex societal problems (Herrero et al., 2018). Thus, there is a process to integrate research and practice (Repko and Sot), which is often also referred to as knowledge coproduction or more specifically action research. The imperative of engaging with wider forms of knowledge than that generated by scientists, TDR has the “desire to actively apply knowledge to the betterment of man and society (Mahan, 1970, pp. 194-195)”. focuses on complex and societally relevant problems and aims to contribute to their solution and therefore is inherently future-oriented.

Co-producing useful knowledge requires extensive stakeholder engagement. A process is designed that brings together scientific knowledge, practitioners' real-life experiences and societal experimentations (Herrero et al., 2019, Pohl et al., 2017; Kalinauskaite, et al., 2021). Participants jointly develop approaches that lead to mutual understanding and respect for diverse knowledge, viewpoints, and methodologies (Kalinauskaite, et al., 2021; Schneider & Buser, 2018). As a result, new theoretical perspectives, and practical methodologies may emerge to solve a societal problem emerge (Grange, 2017).

However, there are major challenges involved. Scholars assume that the outputs of TDR include new theoretical perspectives and practical methodologies to solve a societal problem, but co-production process can fail due to insufficient attention to power (Turnhout et al., 2020; Chambers et al., 2022) because power inequalities cannot just be 'managed away' (Turnhout et al., 2020).. Equality among participants is not self-evident; elite actors have more resources and can shape the process to serve their interests or because scientific knowledge has a stronger authority in comparison to other knowledge systems. Participatory processes are often dominated by a depoliticized discourse that uses scientific arguments to evoke universalized ideas (Turnhout et al., 2020, p. 16). Co-production processes can empower some actors over others where they are subject to political and social pressures (Turnhout et al., 2020). This means that questions about who participates and on what basis are extremely important and require careful consideration, as well as explicit recognition of where biases may emerge (e.g. it is often through researchers' own networks that stakeholder groupings are formed). Further the engagement of the private sector has been unproblematically part of many multi-stakeholder processes to date, given current orthodoxies within development that have promoted private-sector led development and private sector actors as necessary for resolving problems. An uncritical engagement of the private sector is problematic in transformative change processes that question concentrations of power (material and discursive). TDR, being a co-production process, is both a knowledge-making and a political practice, inevitably affected by power imbalances and political structures (Turnhout et al., 2020). co-producing processes with multiple stakeholders will always require decisions that will influence power relations and political structures.

There is growing attention to **decolonisation** in research which is relevant toTc4BE given the producer countries and history of the telecoupled commodities. Postcolonialism is defined as the continued presence of colonialism after the independence of former colonial countries (Mishra & Hodge, 2005), with decolonization being efforts from formerly colonized countries to break from the effects of former colonialism (Lunga, 2008). This implies promoting plurality and questioning dominant power and orthodoxies. In research, positivist science has a dominant position, hence making space for plural forms of knowledge is necessary to resolve complex sustainability challenges through transformative change (Abson et al, ref). The position of the researcher shifts from external observer of reality, testing universal facts, to a participating researcher who shapes the process through engagement (West et al, ref). New methods and processes emerge from this thinking, including a goal to generate situated knowledge of utility to stakeholders, and a need to be reflexive – i.e. for researchers to explicitly explore ethical and political tensions inherent in their methods; these tensions will never be resolved, but can be productively explored and brought to the fore to unsettle the boundaries between the disciplines to deliver transdisciplinary insights. Achieving this within individual research projects can be challenging, as wider research systems require setting of research outcomes in advance of action research processes and outputs may not be seen as rigorous as more conventional research approaches (PhD ref).

4.2 Participatory Action Research (PAR)

Participatory approaches in international development have now been in operation for decades, but analysts have long noted the ‘tyranny of participation’ (Cooke and Kothari, 2003), in which the discourse of participation is largely determined by an unfair and/or an illegitimate exercise of power. Turnhout et al (2021) point to an ambition-practice gap, as many transdisciplinary processes become instrumentalized in practice (Bartels and Wittmayer, 2020). Avoiding this requires deep reflection among the team on the mandate of the process, and how to avoid reinforcing power inequalities and orthodoxies through a ‘learning as usual’ approach – especially so, given our focus on transformative change.

PAR is a research approach that emphasizes collaboration between researchers and the participants of the study. It aims to address social issues and promote positive change by involving the affected community in the research process. The primary goals of PAR are to generate knowledge, empower participants, and foster social transformation. In action research, the act of observing is understood to engage researchers in the social context in which they are working, thus having an influence on that context and this raises ethical imperatives pointing to co-production approaches. The inescapable effects of their presence (West et al, Bartels and W) means that researchers should recognize these world-effects when considering the choices of methods employed (West et al). Examples of PAR processes are given below.

Figure 2 PAR processes

PAR primarily focuses on research, social transformation, and empowering marginalized communities. It aims to address specific social issues and create actionable knowledge. Social learning, on the other hand, is a broader concept that focuses on how individuals acquire knowledge and learn from others within a social context, without necessarily being tied to a specific research agenda.

Figure 3 PAR processes

4.3 Multi-stakeholder social learning

Social learning can be defined as a process in which learning occurs *in a social context through interactions and processes, where a change in understanding has taken place in the individuals involved which goes beyond the individual and becomes situated within wider social units or communities of practice* (Reed et al. 2010). Drawing on insights from psychology about how people learn from observations of the behaviour of others in social interactions, multi-stakeholder social learning processes can be used to build trust and enable participants to better understand the perspectives and values of others.

Social learning can be employed by Multi-Stakeholder Platforms (MSPs) and facilitated at and between different scales – from local and subnational to national, regional, and global. The approach can be used to advance knowledge and skills but critically it also generates ownership of the process, leading to increased motivation and willingness to act. It can be used in challenging and controversial contexts, such as land rights disputes and conflicts. The aim is not necessarily to build consensus but to build shared understanding of the values and perspectives of others through joint learning, as a precursor to action and finding of solutions.

Social learning can therefore occur in any context where there is social interaction, as this is how humans learn. However, in intentional processes, it can be used with multiple stakeholders to bring different forms of knowledge to a process. It thus will occur in PAR approaches, TDR approaches and in specific methods such as Citizen Assemblies.

Using intentional, multi-stakeholder facilitated social learning can bring diverse values and perspectives to the table, using a structured learning cycle process. However, it is vulnerable to the same challenges as TDR –so that attention to power dynamics, during stakeholder identification and engagement), to ensuring inclusiveness and plural views in the learning process, is critical (Metz, Ingram et al. 2023) .

4.4 Comparisons

We aim to reach many of the TCforBE objectives through PAR and social learning processes, where we also talk about co-design/creation-production/generation, PAR processes and social learning processes - which overlap. PAR and social learning both involve collaboration, dialogue and shared

decision-making. A distinction may be drawn between PAR which is often carried out at local and sub-regional levels, and focuses on an issue, with multi-stakeholder social learning which explicitly focuses on joint activities driven by those who need to learn and recognizing that diverse values need to be mobilized and shared in addressing complex sustainability challenges. Social learning refers to the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, attitudes, or behaviours through interactions with others within a social context. It recognizes that learning is not only an individual process but also a collective one that occurs through observation, imitation, and social interactions. Learning processes might particularly emphasize learning in social and cultural contexts, and exposure to diverse perspectives and experiences, with active engagement in discussions, sharing of ideas and co-creating knowledge through collaboration. Observation and imitation are also understood in social psychology to be important in learning and behaviour change processes, hence can be part of multi-stakeholder social learning that seeks to effect values shifts. While deep worldviews (broad values as per IPBES Values Assessment, *ibid*) can be harder to shift, it is clearly possible to change specific values (as per IPBES, *ibid*).

Table 2 Key concepts

Concepts	Example Definitions Key features	Limitations?
Action Research	Experiential learning processes in internal cognitive processes (Kolb) Critical and relational approach	Facilitation skills,
Co-production/co-generate	collaboration between researchers and others with a stake in a project in its governance, priority-setting, conducting of research, and knowledge translation (Holmes).	Time, costs, Facilitation skills,
Co-creation /co-design	approach to creative practice, particularly within the public sector and research, with roots in participatory design and involves using Influence and Participation methods to understand what people with lived experience need and want.	Time, costs, Facilitation skills,
Social learning	Originates from social psychology, noted that individuals learn through observing interactions in social contexts. Widely used in health and natural resources management, and in national learning processes to shape policy processes (Lamboll et al)	Requires sophisticated facilitation skills. Uncertainty can be uncomfortable for those used to more linear, structured processes with pre-defined specific objectives and results. Such flexibility is often at odds with donor funding.
Transdisciplinarity	For some it generates integrated knowledge, for others it recognizes the incommensurability of different forms of knowledge and ontologies and seeks to avoid epistemic violences, i.e. transcending integrative approaches to more pluralistic ones.	Willingness to listen and understand and work with different people/communities of practices/societies with different views, values, methods, approaches

5. Social Learning cycles

5.1 Learning cycles to structure social learning

Facilitating participatory structured learning cycles can provide an underlying 'rhythm' to the process of learning – a pattern that is easy to follow as it provides a guiding structure to the process. Each cycle involves joint reflection on learning priorities, planning of and implementation of creative learning activities, and reflection to inform action strategies. Over time, this builds cumulative knowledge and experience. The steps to follow in a learning cycle include:

- **Identify learning priorities:** Diagnose/ frame / conceptualise an issue
- **Plan learning activities:** Jointly discuss and decide on the nature of the learning activities and their timing, who will participate in different activities, any tools and methods that need to be used or developed, how the activities will be documented and by whom and anticipated outcomes.
- **Conduct learning activities:** Conduct the planned joint learning activities (field visits, studies, pilots, etc) and document progress.
- **Reflect** on the learning activities, using the Theory of Change (ToC) – What has been achieved and why? What has not been achieved and why? Which assumptions held true? See the ToC tool for more details.
- **Feed insights into strategic planning and move to next learning cycle**

Example: Learning Cycle Methodologies

NRI have successfully used this approach in various recent projects: the UK AID SAIRLA programme, an EC Global Climate Change Alliance project in Malawi, and in a UK AID evaluation to support learning and adaptive management of DFID's Partnerships for Forests programme.

Example: Social learning involving multiple stakeholders in Africa focusing on sustainable agriculture.

In the UK Aid funded programme called Sustainable Agricultural Intensification Research and Learning in Africa (SAIRLA), social learning was facilitated in five countries, Ethiopia, Ghana, Malawi, Tanzania, and Zambia. Diverse stakeholders were brought together in National Learning Alliances (NLAs) to enable social learning to inform policy and investment decisions around the contested issue of Sustainable Agricultural Intensification. A broader dialogue process allowed a flow of communication where the conversation can take many directions and concludes with diverse representation of voices and issues, building local ownership. Shorter learning cycles were more oriented to deliberative decision-making around SAI-related policy processes. In Malawi and Zambia, this included highly contested policies and legislation around customary land tenure.

Figure 4 Cumulative social learning cycles – learning builds up over time with new cycles

Example: Using Social Learning in a virtual learning cycle on engaging the private sector responsible agricultural investment in the LandCollaborative Learning Cycle with NRI

The topic of whether and how to engage the private sector is not straightforward – there are both pros and cons to engagement, and the challenges are significant. LandCollaborative partners have a wealth of experience and contextual knowledge on land rights and private sector impacts around the world. Hence a social learning process provided an opportunity to bring these specialists together to explore the pros and cons together.

In 2021–22, a Learning Cycle on engaging the private sector for responsible agricultural investment was undertaken with 27 participants from 12 multi-stakeholder platforms in 12 countries¹. Organised online due to the COVID 19 pandemic, the structured learning cycle included both interactive learning sessions covering some of the basics of land and responsible agricultural investment (RAI) alongside participatory structured learning cycles. Following early discussions to facilitate articulation of learning priorities by the participants, an open-ended list of possible themes was suggested, from which participants could choose and to which they could add. These were then ranked by participants in country groups². The highest ranked theme was “Exploring practical strategies for and experiences of engaging the private sector”. Based on participants’ interests and suggestions, NRI drafted an overall learning objective, plus 3 sub-themes and associated learning outcomes – see below. The overall objective for Learning theme 1 was to explore practical strategies and experiences to inform the development of MSP private-sector engagement strategies through collective learning, which results in more equitable and sustainable private sector land investments. Specific sub-themes (and their anticipated outcomes in italics):

- Communication and learning to bridge differences in perceptions, build understanding and enhance trust amongst diverse civil society organisations (CSOs), the private sector and other actors. *Improved understanding and practical experience gained by participants of how to communicate and build trust with the private sector and amongst diverse MSP actors.*
- Private-sector motivation and willingness to engage in responsible investment. *Improved understanding gained by participants of private-sector perspectives and drivers of decision making.*
- Enabling environment for advancing responsible agri-investment by the private sector (company obligations, legislation, capacity, policies, regional processes). *Improved understanding gained by participants of the enabling environment and how it can be informed/ changed by MSP members.*

Participants identified their learning priorities and then split into groups to take different themes to explore. Each group developed a plan – based on a table with columns for ‘reflect’, ‘plan learning’, ‘conduct learning’, etc. and agreed on dates. The process occurred over 12 months.

- Group 1 explored how to build understanding and enhance trust amongst diverse actors through two main activities. Firstly, participants consulted companies that they already have links with and /or felt could be approached to explore communication and trust issues and the results were shared with other group members. Secondly, participants shared their experiences of engaging with the private sector. Some of the documented experiences were further developed into case studies for wider sharing.
- Group 2 explored private-sector incentives and motivation with respect to RAI. Participants devised a checklist of questions to guide interviews with investors, conducted a series of interviews by clarifying the purpose of the meeting, confirming confidentiality, and sharing questions in advance. The findings from the interviews, focused on private-sector perspectives, were shared with the group.
- Group 3 explored the enabling environment including its definitions, potential entry points for action to change conditions, and requirements for private-sector companies and investors in agricultural land investments.

The findings were shared with the wider Learning Cycle participants in a participatory workshop and fed into the co-generated document on Guidance, link [here](#).

5.2 Nested learning processes

An MSP can use social learning to underpin its overall approach, as well as to advance understanding and action on specific themes. Learning cycles can be facilitated at different scales, but they are interconnected, with have differing objectives. A broader process of joint learning and reflection (e.g. at MSP level) can focus on a major issue to support dialogue which leads to enhanced and shared understanding. Nested within this broader learning cycle, are mini-cycles which are deliberative in nature and involve joint learning and reflection on specific challenges or opportunities, ideally leading to solutions and decisions. For example, MSPs may engage in learning and reflection on people-centred land governance (dialogues involving multiple stakeholders), with smaller working groups exploring specific issues (e.g. how to engage the private sector, working with a small group of companies to develop new norms on RAI). In the LandCollaborative learning cycle, a similar nested approach to the learning cycles was adopted.

5.3 Limitations of learning cycles

Can take energy and resources to run such SL processes well and there are uncertainties about outcomes and perceptions of academic rigour.

Ideally, to have the greatest value, the social learning process should encourage deeper learning, rather than merely reinforcing existing perspectives. To do this requires particular attention. Organisational management theory points to 'triple loop learning', i.e. learning should not only focus on 'How can I / we do what I am already doing better?' (single loop learning), or 'Am I / we doing the right thing?' (double loop learning), but also 'Who should decide on what is the best approach?' 'And what are the more fundamental shifts required?' (triple loop learning). For example, with respect to people-centred land governance, an MSP may consider how to do what they are currently doing better (single loop learning), but this may ignore the potential to shift corporate practice (as well as the risks of legitimizing private-sector concessions). They may also consider if there are different strategic actions they could undertake, such as seeking to work directly with reform-oriented private-sector companies or working on specific aspects of the enabling environment to create conditions for more diverse investment, with private-sector investment following international standards (VGGT and CFS-RAI etc) (double loop learning). Finally, they may also consider who should decide on appropriate approaches (e.g. do they have a broad spectrum of types of members) and what the approach should be (e.g. not only adversarial advocacy, but social learning) and if more fundamental shifts are required (e.g. changing national narratives on the value of smallholder farming and/or national measures of wellbeing rather than GDP as progress) (triple loop learning).

¹ Two main forms of learning were facilitated: a) interactive learning sessions which explored key fundamentals in responsible land investment and people-centred land governance and b) collective issue-based learning.

² Thirteen themes were suggested, ranging from general issues such as achieving greater transparency, exploring practical engagement strategies, and facilitating community dialogue and strengthening community rights for agribusiness investments, to addressing specific types of investments, for instance in forest crops or public-private partnerships. For full details see the [InfoNote on Learning Needs assessment](#) for the learning cycle.

TC thinking increasingly points to a need to question orthodoxies in food, land and economy domains, and this means giving space for alternative visions and perspectives which challenge orthodoxies – given that the current orthodoxies have underpinned massive socio-ecological damage. **This means that space needs to be created – especially in food and agriculture learning – for informed perspectives which question modern industrial food systems. Hence, there needs to be more emphasis on non-corporate and non-technocratic organisations and solutions and creating safe spaces for alternative voices and social movements.**

5.4 Transdisciplinary research capacities and capabilities

Social learning, participatory action research and co-production are all kinds of TDR. In a sense they are longstanding methodologies and approaches which seek to facilitate collaboration between disciplines and plural forms of knowledge. **Whether something constitutes TDR on definitions; for some authors it is about integrating knowledge, but we propose that it is about more than this – it is about unsettling boundaries between disciplines recognizing that some forms of knowledge have side-lined others under coloniality. Positivist science as a whole has more dominance (as well as immense practical value) compared to other forms of knowledge such as Indigenous knowledge and relational philosophies.**

In positivist sciences, methods selection is neutral and used to assess reality that exists beyond the researcher. The contention from critical and interpretive social sciences (West et al, 2022) is that methods are not 'neutral, technical tools that researchers can pick up and use to learn about a reality 'out there', with researcher competency being learning to apply technical routines and procedures to obtain reliable results', but the choice has ethical implications. A key reason for ethical and political tensions between methods is that 'bringing methods together often reveals their tacit, inherently contestable, and sometimes directly opposing assumptions about reality and how it can and should be known' (West and Schill, 2022). Methods have 'world-affecting' effects (Wingrove cited by West and Schill, 2022). Research methods do not only describe different realities but also inevitably participate in and help to create the realities they describe' (West and Schill, 2022).

This difference of perspective is not something that can be resolved or managed away – so TDR approaches need to address it explicitly, learn to live with and profit from it.

A key competence for TDR is to be able to 'recognize and negotiate the ethical-political dimensions of research methods as a key competency in mixed methods, inter-, and transdisciplinary and co-production research, particularly for researchers in fields like environment, health and education' (West and Schill, 2022). *'For example, an Indigenous elder may feel ethically compelled to resist practices that they feel perpetuate colonialism; an interpretivist may feel ethically compelled to resist practices that they feel lead to the instrumental control of citizens; and a positivist may feel ethically compelled to resist practices that they feel reduce trust in collective institutions. Indeed, as we have engaged with these ethical-political dimensions we have sensed ourselves shifting from a simple "both-and" approach to mixing methods, towards what Schwartz-Shea (2006: p. 326) refers to as "reflexive"'. Thus, it is necessary to 'nurture an ongoing critical dialogue...where we can mutually interrogate our aims, intentions and positionalities in our research, the ways we engage with participants, and the (variable) effects of our research in society'. They propose a variety of approaches e.g. book club type reflection, use of researcher video diaries and reflection process, which has potential*

relevance for TC for BE. For our project we are developing a reflexivity plan, but this effort is central to TDR working which itself is key for TC.

West et al (2022) identify some key questions to help researchers to recognize the ethical-political dimensions of mixed method research (ontological, epistemological, axiological and social effects). Suggested methods for a) practices – reading groups in philosophy, ethics, and social studies of science; personal video diaries, group facilitated dialogues; b) skills – reflexivity and accountability, deliberation, practical wisdom. West and Schill use independent facilitators. Following West et al's suggestion on 'putting relationality into practice', this essentially means having an open stance on concepts, and recognizing that there are plural ways of understanding and being in the world. It also means resisting singular notions of desirable transformation or of singular policy prescriptions. A plurality of differing interpretations of any context are equally valid, each with its associated conditioning normative values, affective styles and relations, ontological assumptions, epistemic practices, and notions of 'evidence'. This also then the case for emerging recommendations - with each relevant understanding and associated recommendation, the particular conditions under which it might be held to be valid need to be clearly articulated, if plurality is to be addressed fully. This means that it is not correct to develop singular solutions; it requires different perspectives to be clearly articulated and then this informs decision-making. If not, then this is how certain perspectives are obscured and suppressed, the obvious example being indigenous knowledge. (see Kenya case Q methodology doc).

For West et al, depending upon where a research project is in its cycle, it is possible to a) work forwards from relations, or b) work backs from existing concepts – in both cases to generate situated, usable concepts. In the TC4BE case, the purpose of an overall conceptual article would be to explain this approach and see how we might add/differ, and also to apply it to food systems / territories thinking and TC.

There are limits to TDR when research funders require specific outcomes in advance of a flexible, learning process. In TC4BE have researcher-driven activities that we have to deliver on, but we need to facilitate TDR processes that engage with public forms of knowledge (e.g. Indigenous and Local Communities) and not only positivist scientific work, but also critical social sciences.

5.5 Rural Imaginaries – using Arts Based methods and a Transdisciplinary approach

In WP5 a design will be created for the rural imaginaries work. There are different ways of approaching this, but one option is to employ arts-based methods.

Arts-based methods (ABM) are gaining increasing attention with respect to transformative change (TC) and transdisciplinary research (TR). They can bring unique value in the exploration, understanding and communication of complex, multifaceted problems including in challenging orthodoxies. They have not been employed significantly in relation to sustainability challenges, including biodiversity loss, and issues of equity and justice in relation to nature and ecological issues – until recently. There is now a blossoming of new approaches which have value for the TC for BE project and have been envisioned as part of the project since the Concept Note and full proposal, particularly with respect to the rural imaginaries work which combines ABM and critical social sciences as an innovative entry point to engaging communities. They can be used more widely in the social learning processes. There are also limitations – as with any research methods – which are indicated below.

Pros of Arts Based Methods

Creativity and innovation: Arts-based approaches foster creative thinking and innovative problem-solving. They encourage exploration of alternative perspectives, challenges to existing assumptions, and generate novel ideas. The arts provide *unconventional* ways of representing and communicating research findings, which can lead to fresh insights and breakthroughs.

Experiential Knowledge: is central to ABM, which can engage the senses and the body, allowing for embodied and experiential knowledge. They enable researchers and participants to engage with the research topic on a deeper, more personal level, beyond intellectual understanding. This experiential knowledge can provide valuable insights into complex issues that might be difficult to capture through traditional methods alone and can be applied to landscape and food research.

Multimodal Communication: The arts offer diverse modes of communication, including visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and performative elements. These multimodal approaches can enhance the accessibility and reach of research findings. They have the potential to engage a wider audience, including those who may not be traditionally involved or interested in academic research, thus fostering broader societal impact.

Boundary crossing and integration: Transdisciplinary research aims to transcend disciplinary boundaries and integrate diverse perspectives and knowledge domains. Arts-based approaches may encourage interdisciplinary collaboration by bridging the gaps between different fields of expertise. They facilitate dialogue, mutual understanding, and shared meaning-making among researchers from various disciplines, as well as with non-academic stakeholders.

Emotions and aesthetic engagement: The arts have the power to evoke emotions and create aesthetic experiences. They can help researchers and participants connect with complex and abstract concepts on an emotional and empathetic level. This emotional engagement can deepen the understanding of research topics, foster empathy, and potentially lead to transformative changes in attitudes and behaviors.

Reflexivity and critical inquiry: Arts-based approaches often involve reflective and reflexive practices, encouraging researchers to critically examine their own assumptions, biases, and positions within the research process. They promote self-awareness, introspection, and ongoing dialogue about the researcher's role, values, and ethical considerations.

ABM may facilitate more meaningful community engagement and empower participants, particularly marginalized groups, to actively contribute to the research process. They provide platforms for community members to express their perspectives, voice their concerns, and shape the research agenda. This participatory approach can lead to more relevant and socially just outcomes.

Thus, ABM can complement more conventional research approaches to achieve more holistic types of understanding. Additionally, and with respect to transformative change, they are important for helping to question hegemonies.

There are various challenges including subjectivity and interpretation, expertise and skills requirements, representation and ethical considerations, limited generalizability, time and resource constraints, audience engagement and accessibility, evaluation and assessment challenges.

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